

AUTOMATED CABLE COUPLING ANALYSIS

SOFTWARE FOR EMC PREDICTION

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Abstract - Electromagnetic (EM) coupling between cables containing shielded twisted pairs can cause system degradation, i.e. powerline noise induced onto cables used for communication.

Software, which uses mathematical models of differential and common-mode coupling between shielded twisted pairs, is described. The differential mode coupling model is derived from Ampere's law and the Biot-Savart law. The common mode coupling model is based on the percent imbalance in cable shield current and inductance due to cable shield distance from a ground plane.

EM data tables and a set of routines employing these models have been generated using Structured Query Language (SQL) embedded in FORTRAN. A unique approach has been taken to ensure correct results and reduce user error. The program accesses a large existing knowledge base of cable electrical and physical properties, requiring only cable designators and positions from a user to obtain an interference evaluation.

Introduction

Coupling of electromagnetic fields from power cables to signal lines is prevalent in many existing cable configurations. Spacing requirements exist for configuration design, i.e. for proper spacing of shipboard cables, the "Handbook of Shipboard Electromagnetic Shielding Practices" can be used [1]. These spacings were obtained using the Biot -Savart / Ampere differential mode model.

The shielding practices handbook did not consider common-mode coupling between cables due to the complexity of modeling the problem. Showers and Peters of the University of Pennsylvania have generated a common-mode coupling model with limited applicability to shipboard cables [2]. The limitations of both the differential and common -mode models are discussed later.

To assist in determining the expected coupling of low frequency magnetic fields between shielded twisted pairs, Automated Cable Coupling Software (ACCS), has been created. ACCS allows a designer to simply specify cables and receive an accurate prediction of EM interference (EMI) based on differential coupling (and common mode coupling if it is applicable).

ACCS is written in VAX FORTRAN and ORACLE SQL under VMS 4.7, and uses TEMPLATE graphics software for diagrams and output. It is menu selectable from NUSC's EMC predictions program [3,4].

Description of Solvable Problems

This program/data base system is designed to analyze proposed and existing cable configurations for electromagnetic coupling between power and signal lines. An existing configuration is defined as a room where any cable which is to be evaluated has its position in the room stored in the data base as pairs of coordinates.

This underscores the difference between using a handbook to obtain a spacing requirement and using software to analyze induced voltage over frequency as a function of spacing. An engineer may evaluate the effect of induced voltage on a signal line; a spacing requirement offers no insight into the coupling present.

The database contains all the cable properties required by the EMI coupling models for the MIL-C-915 set of cables. The cable currents and voltages as a function of frequency are also resident in the data base for any existant configuration. All properties of a proposed cable configuration must be entered into the data base before the analyses can begin.

Method of Solution

Input

The data base (Fig 1) is structured so that all parameters required by the analysis equations are available. As stated above, to ensure effective program performance, analysis of a cable is not permitted unless all supporting information for the cable is present in the data base.

Cable Coupling Data Tables

Fig 1

Consequently, parameters for all cables available for selection are entered into the data base prior to use of the program. Figure 2 shows all the physical and electrical cable properties necessary to calculate differential and common mode coupling of low frequency magnetic fields between shielded twisted pairs.

Calculations

A Voltage Transfer Ratio (VTR) is defined as voltage present at the far end of a receptor cable (due to coupling) divided by the source cable driving voltage. This would be V_{emi} / V_s in figure 2.

Cable Coupling Analysis Parameters

Fig 2

The differential mode coupling equations used in ACCS (Fig 3) result in voltage transfer ratios based on wire spacing, wire pitch, loading, and cable spacing, frequency and transfer impedance. These are the same equations used to develop the spacing requirements in the shipboard EM shielding handbook [1].

The common-mode coupling equations derived by Showers and Peters [2] use the assumption that an imbalance in wire pair current creates a uniform constant azimuthal current in the wire pair shield. Possible sources of such currents could be nonuniformities in transmission lines or unbalanced sources or loads. The further assumption that the shield can now be treated as a single wire over a ground plane results in the VTR given in figure 4. The result is that common mode coupling of shielded twisted pairs depends on cable inductance, percent imbalance in wire current, shield transfer impedance, source loading and frequency. This result applies only to low frequency coupling of magnetic fields between short cables whose shields are tied to a common, physically close, ground plane.

$$VTR = \frac{2.54 (4\pi)^2 A_r A_s P_r Z_r Z_s e^{\frac{(-2\pi d)}{P_s}}}{f u P_s R \sqrt{d P_s}}$$

**DIFFERENTIAL MODE
COUPLING
VOLTAGE TRANSFER RATIO**

Definitions

R = source load (ohms)	A = wire spacing (cm)
d = cable separation (cm)	P = wire pitch (cm)
f = frequency (Hz)	Z = transfer impedance of cable (ohms)
u = permeability (uH/m)	

Subscripts in equations refer to source cable (s) and receptor cable (r).

Differential Mode EM Coupling Analysis Equations for Shielded Twisted Cables

Fig 3

The transparent operation of ACCS, involves Standard Query Language (SQL) statements which scan the data base and retrieve all necessary equation parameters. SQL statements also fetch the path and signal arrays.

The actual positions of the cables within a room are represented by the path table in the data base. The position of a cable is defined in a plane by a sequence of X-Y pairs. The entire length of a cable must be defined.

The voltages present on the cables are represented in a similar manner; X-Y pairs correspond to voltage (dBV) and frequency (Hz). These arrays must also exist for the cable to be selected.

ACCS calculates spacing and length quantities from the path arrays and channels them to the appropriate VTR routine. The VTR routine takes that information and the other previously mentioned quantities (current, pitch, transfer impedance, etc.) and generates the VTR for that cable set.

The VTR is then multiplied by the voltage of the source cable, at each frequency, to obtain the estimated induced voltage.

Output

Obtaining an EMC analysis is then reduced to a user studying a computer-generated diagram of a cable configuration and selecting source and susceptor cables.

The flow chart of ACCS shows this simplicity (Fig 5).

The resulting analysis shows voltage as a function of frequency for each cable and the radiated voltage induced on the susceptible cable. If the induced voltage is greater than the voltage present on the susceptible cable, at any frequency, then EM Interference (EMI) is indicated at those frequencies.

Limitation / Verification

These analyses apply only to frequencies below 10 MHz and only when the cable length to wavelength ratio is less than .05.

The necessary comparison of this theoretical work with empirical data would be lengthy and out of the scope of this document.

However, the shielding handbook [1] has been used for years and has produced effective results in eliminating differential mode coupling. The resulting comparison would be an error check of the software more than an evaluation of differential mode coupling theory.

$VTR = \frac{b_r b_s m L Z_r Z_s}{2 \pi f R l_r l_s}$	COMMON-MODE COUPLING VOLTAGE TRANSFER RATIO
$l = 200 \ln (2h/r) \text{ nH/m}$	SELF - INDUCTANCE OF CABLES
$m = 100 \ln (1+(2h/d)^2)$	MUTUAL INDUCTANCE OF CABLES
<u>Definitions</u>	
Z = transfer impedance of cable (ohms)	R = source load (ohms)
d = cable separation (cm)	b = % imbalance of current in cable (%)
f = frequency (Hz)	L = cable length (m)
l = self inductance of cable (nH/m)	h = height above plane (cm)
m = cable mutual inductance (nH/m)	r = shield radius (cm)
Subscripts in equations refer to source cable (s) and receptor cable (r).	

Common Mode EM Coupling Analysis Equations for Shielded Twisted Cables

Fig 4

Situations in which the common mode coupling equations may have valid applications must make the common mode VTR demonstrate a significant value at some frequency.

Using the common mode coupling VTR one can make some assumptions, derive a constraint and envision a situation in which some common mode coupling is expected. Since the cable length, source load and the shield surface transfer impedance are constrained by the installation, the variables to consider are the percent imbalance in wire current, the inductance of the cables, and the shield grounding configuration.

First assume a small but significant imbalance in the wires and the appropriate grounding configuration, i.e. both ends of both shields connected to a large metal surface like a ships hull. Then if mutual inductance exists, and the cable self inductance is low, then some common mode coupling is expected.

Mutual inductance between cables is proportional to the natural log of one plus the square of twice the cable height / cable separation ratio. (cable height is measured from the ground plane, see figures 2 and 4). A ratio which is greater than 0.655 will cause mutual inductance to be significant , i.e. greater than 100 nH/m.

Cable self inductance is proportional to the natural log of twice the cable height / cable radius ratio . A ratio which is less than e/2 (~1.35) causes cable self inductance to be low, i.e. less than 200 nH/m. A ratio less than or equal to one has no meaning.

The resulting constraint for considering common mode coupling is that the cable height from the ground plane must be greater than .655 times the cable separation and between 1.35 and 0.5 times the cable radius.

The following conditions would then provide a source for some empirical data to validate this theory. The data and theory taken together would provide insight into possible cable configuration problems.

(1) Several shielded twisted pairs do a short (~3m) run through a metallic compartment and the shields are terminated at entry and exit.

(2) The pairs have unbalanced sources and loads outside the compartment.

(3) The shields have high transfer impedances.

(4) $0.5 < \text{Cable distance to ground plane} / \text{radius of cable} < 1.35$

(5) $0.655 <$ Cable distance to ground plane / separation of cables

Flow Diagram For Coupling Software

Fig 5

Conclusion

This shows how complete the automation of an EMC model may be made using SQL embedded in FORTRAN, and provides access to both differential and common mode type cable coupling analyses.

Verification of differential mode coupling models is implicitly given by the success of the spacing handbook [1]. An experiment is proposed to verify the accuracy of common mode coupling effects.

Acknowledgements

Appreciation is extended to R. Showers and S. Peters, University of Pennsylvania for development of the equations and theory present in this software.

This paper was prepared under Project No. A51000 "Ship's Below-Decks Electromagnetic Compatibility Program", Principal Investigator D. S. Dixon (Code 3431). The Sponsoring Activity is the Office of the Chief of Naval Research/Office of Naval Technology, Submarine Technology, Program Element Manager G. Remmers (Code 233). The Submarine Technology Block Program Manager is L. Cathers (Code 0114) of the David W. Taylor Research Center.

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